

The Role of the Organizational Technology as a moderating Variable: Entrepreneurial Orientation and Organizational Survival of Hotels in Port Harcourt

Thomas C. Okoisama & Ojiabo Ukoha

Abstract:

The study investigated the relationship between Entrepreneurial Orientation and Organizational Survival, with Organizational Technology as the moderating variable. The cross sectional survey design was adopted. The population for the study consists of 150 owners of hotels in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. Exploratory Factor Analysis was used to validate the instrument, and preliminary analysis were performed to check normality, linearity and equality of variance. The Krejcie and Morgan's formula was used to determine the sample size of 108. Copies of questionnaire were administered to an adjusted sample size of 136 owners of hotels. Data obtained from 115 retrieved and usable copies of the questionnaires were analyzed by means of the Statistical Program for Social Science, and Analysis and Moments of Structures. Descriptive statistics were generated, while the Structural Equation Modelling was deployed to test hypotheses, using a reflective, reflective and recursive model approach to predict the dependent variable. The results revealed that all the Pro-activeness has positive significant relationships with the measure of Organizational survival; Strategic partnership, while Organizational Technology significantly moderates the relationship between Entrepreneurial Orientation and Organizational Survival of Hotels in Port Harcourt. The study recommends that hotel management and owners should focus on redesigning service to actualize distinctiveness, in order to gain competitive advantage and ultimately survive. The study contributes to knowledge by presenting a structural fitness and a detailed assessment of the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and organizational survival, using technology as a moderator, by means of structural equations modelling. Hotel owners should manage technology effectively as it affects the influence of entrepreneurial orientation on organizational survival.

IJSB

Accepted 02 March 2019
Published 03 March 2019
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.2582477

Keywords: technology, entrepreneurial orientation, organizational survival, pro-activeness, strategic partnership.

About Author

Thomas C. Okoisama, (Corresponding Author), Department of Management, Faculty of Management Sciences, University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

Ojiabo Ukoha, Department of Management, Faculty of Management Sciences, University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

Introduction

Organizations are built up to survive and prevail by being gainful to their proprietors and partners (Stam & Elfring, 2008). Organizational survival has turned into a basic business objective, at a time when organizations are likely to accomplish more with lesser assets, and additionally outflank contenders and emphatically affect the group and setting after some time (John, Micheal & Cassiu, 2017; and Gaboul & Fais, 2015). As supported by Lekhanya (2016), business survival can be viewed as an unwritten law that guide each firm. This suggests each organization, particularly should see survival as a flat out objective (Gross, 2002). Thusly, survival should be viewed as a basic objective that guides the choice activities of business leaders and adherents, consistently and constantly. The significance of organizational survival in addressing the requirements of the clients, and guaranteeing a perfect society where the necessities of all are met, can't be over accentuated. As confirmed by John et al., (2017), organizational survival supersedes each different objectives and goals (profit, sales, cost minimization) of the firm, passing by the way that the firm works in an exceptionally unique condition where advancement is driving the market consistently, where customer demand from the firm in a speed that is quick evolving. Given the business condition that is described by high speed of progress and a disturbing rate of vulnerability, business survival remains the fundamental point of each firm. Artisan and Lekhanya (2014) noticed that organizations seek after a few objectives including profit expansion yet most of their exertion ought to and should be committed to guaranteeing survival after some time. As contended by Gaboul and Fais (2015), organizational survival shows in profit margins, market share controlled in the business, the measure of the firm, the age of the firm and the general budgetary state of the firm in connection to its capacity to get together with requests of customers, investors and all parties of interest.

The observed gaps based on the empirical literature review, shows that there are several studies on organizational survival, however one thing that has been least discussed, is from the perspective of entrepreneurial orientation. Hence, there is dearth in literature in the connection between Entrepreneurial Orientation and Organizational Survival. Second, there is insufficient literature on the moderating role of organizational technology on entrepreneurial orientation and organizational survival. Moreover, studies that have utilized structural equations modeling (SEM) with AMOS software, to quantify the impact of entrepreneurial orientation on organizational survival is scant. It is based on that fact that this work, is structured to examine how entrepreneurial orientation will lead to organizational survival of hotels in Port Harcourt, using technology as a moderating variable.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of entrepreneurial orientation

Wang (2008) contended that entrepreneurial orientation (EO) is a noteworthy factor for a firm's prosperity. The corporate association works in a dynamic business condition where future stream of wage is ruled by vulnerability, in that capacity association need to deliberately look to expand each giving open door in the market (Zhou, Wu & Luo, 2007)). Entrepreneurial orientation can be viewed as a vital device received by corporate pioneers to realize association objectives and destinations, maintain vision, in this way making competitive advantage in the commercial center (Wiklund & Shepherd, 2003). This declaration that entrepreneurial orientation adds to firm achievement and productivity has been worked together by scientists, for example, Kuhn, Sassmannshausen and Zollin (2010) and Rauch, Wiklund, Lumpkin, and Frese (2009). This is in accordance with the contention of

authors like Ireland, Hitt, and Sirmon (2003) and Hult et al. (2003) that contended that entrepreneurial orientation encourages simple market entrance prompting high gainfulness of the association. As confirmed by Rauch et al (2009) that association that have solid entrepreneurial orientation seems to perform preferable in the market over those with little orientation. A comparable view was shared by Ireland, Hitt and Sirmon (2003) when he contended that firm entrepreneurial orientation, qualities and procedures are central point that decides the association achievement. Like each other real idea business enterprise definition is profoundly disputable and contrasts by various authors regarding definition and operationalization. Lumpkin and Dess (as cited to in Yu-Ming et al, 2018) stated five measurements that component the entrepreneurial orientation of an association including pro-activeness, innovativeness, competitive aggressiveness, risk-taking, and autonomy. Business ingenuity mirrors the propensity to participate in and encourages new products, upgrade innovativeness, experimentation and inventive procedures. Then again, pro-activeness involves firm roles in misusing and envisioning new chances, present new products and in addition making change towards a product (Gupta & Dultta, 2016). Risk taking involves the readiness to submit assets to experience exercises and tasks which brought about vulnerability of the results (Gupta & Dultta, 2016). Competitive aggressiveness is the power of the organizations to enhance their situation to exceed and surpass their rivals in the market (Gupta & Dultta, 2016). Risk taking involves the association hostile system that is coordinated towards outsmarting contenders and might be very receptive particularly when association forcefully enters a market that an adversary has distinguished (Zechir, 2015). Autonomy alludes to a free activity of individual or groups in guaranteeing thoughts and ideas are being carried out till fruition (Gupta & Dultta, 2016). Autonomy allows workers to perform in a compelling route by being free, self-coordinated, and imaginative.

Concept of Organizational Survival

Organizational survival as noted earlier is the major aim of the organization beyond the profit maximization objectives of the organization. An organizational survival and its competitive advantage, growth and strategy are imbedded implicitly in the organization goals and objectives that require constant investment in resources renewal (Jones & Bartlet, 2008). This propelled Yu-Ming et al., (2018) to argue that firm's survival strategy supersedes every other form of the organization strategy and organization goals and objectives. As argued by the authors, the survival strategy or goals facilitates the achievement of other goals in the organization. As noted, business survival can be compared to an unwritten code of the association that is more essential to the entrepreneur than the composed code.

Adewale, Abolaji and Kolade, (2011) noted that a firm is evaluated in periods of development and advancement as opposed to in ordered years. The stages are combined in a synchronized way, however not every one of the associations accept the distinctive periods of the advancement. As substantiated by Mindy (2010) corporate firm keep up assortment of objective and targets in keeping up the current situation, be that as it may, more prominent part of the association endeavours are secured to keeping up survival after some time.

Organizational Technology

Technology often evolves in certain path dependent ways, contoured and channeled by what might be thought of as technological paradigms (Chen, 2007). A technological paradigm is a pattern of solutions to selected technical problems which derives from certain engineering relationships. A "worldview distinguishes the issues that must be explained and the best approach to ask about them; within a paradigm, research efforts become channeled along

certain trajectories.' Relatedly, new product and process advancements for a specific association are probably going to lie in the innovative neighbourhood of past victories. An entrepreneur who distinguishes which class he or she falls into will think that it's less demanding to embrace the mechanical methodology that suits their need. Innovation improvement, especially inside a specific worldview, continues in total along the way characterized by the worldview. The way that mechanical advancement expands on what went previously, and that quite a bit of it is inferred and exclusive, implies that it for the most part has noteworthy association particular measurements. In addition, an association's specialized abilities are probably going to be "close in" to previous technological accomplishments. Technological progress exhibits strong irreversibility. This follows not just because innovation typically requires specialized investments, but because the evolution of technologies along certain trajectories eliminates the possibility of competition from older technologies, even if relative prices change significantly. Thus mechanical calculators are unlikely to ever replace electronic ones, even if the relative prices of silicon and steel were to switch by a factor of 20 in favour of steel. Innovation is characterized by technological interrelatedness between various subsystems. Linkages to other technologies, to complementary assets, and to users must be maintained if innovation is to be successful". As indicated by Gupta et al., (2016) innovation exchange may present loads of challenges in exchange without the exchange of key people. This can clarify the plain actuality that impersonation frequently forecasts heaps of troubles for the association and the dissemination of innovation relies upon the contending association absorptive limit, and the portability of the designer over the association. Firm innovation progression can be insurance system likewise assumes an imperative job in their key preference in the market (Gupta & Gupta, 2015). Firm that does not ensure its innovation headway may wind up losing the innovation to the adversaries through the portability of its specialists and perception by the contenders.

The moderating role of Technology on Entrepreneurial Orientation and Organizational Survival

Technology often evolves in certain path dependent ways, contoured and channeled by what might be thought of as technological paradigms (Chen, 2007). A technological paradigm is a pattern of solutions to selected technical problems which derives from certain engineering relationships. A "worldview distinguishes the issues that must be explained and the best approach to ask about them; within a paradigm, research efforts become channeled along certain trajectories.' Relatedly, new product and process advancements for a specific association are probably going to lie in the innovative neighborhood of past victories. An entrepreneur who distinguishes which class he or she falls into will think that it's less demanding to embrace the mechanical methodology that suits their need. Innovation improvement, especially inside a specific worldview, continues in total along the way characterized by the worldview. The way that mechanical advancement expands on what went previously, and that quite a bit of it is inferred and exclusive, implies that it for the most part has noteworthy association particular measurements. In addition, an association's specialized abilities are probably going to be "close in" to previous technological accomplishments. Technological progress exhibits strong irreversibility. This follows not just because innovation typically requires specialized investments, but because the evolution of technologies along certain trajectories eliminates the possibility of competition from older technologies, even if relative prices change significantly. Thus mechanical calculators are unlikely to ever replace electronic ones, even if the relative prices of silicon and steel were to

switch by a factor of 20 in favour of steel. Innovation is characterized by technological interrelatedness between various subsystems. Linkages to other technologies, to complementary assets, and to users must be maintained if innovation is to be successful.

The Objectives of the Study:

1. To ascertain the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and organizational survival
2. To determine if organizational technology moderates the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and organizational survival.

Research Hypotheses

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between the pro-activeness and strategic partnership.

Ho1: Technology does not significantly moderate the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and organizational survival.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a cross-sectional survey design, as data was collated on a snap-shot basis. This study aimed at examining the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and organizational survival, as well as to determine if organizational technology moderates the relationship between of entrepreneurial orientation and organizational survival of hotels in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. The population for this study comprises of all the owner-managed hotels, registered with the Rivers State Hotel Proprietors' Association. The accessible population consists of 150 respondents. Since the respondents are the hotel owners, there are in position to express their opinion about the questions relating to the research instrument. The sampling procedure adopted in this study is the simple random sampling technique, which enables each member of the population to have an equal chance of being selected. A sample size of 108 hotel owners was determined using Krejcie and Morgan's formula. Data was collected through questionnaire. The predictor variable-entrepreneurial orientation, was measured by innovativeness, pro-activeness and risk-taking based on the earlier work by Gupta & Gupta (2015). The criterion variable-Organization survival were measured in terms competitiveness, strategic partnership and adaptability respectively. The variables were measured using the 5 point Likert: where 5 = Strongly Agree, 4 = Agree, 3 = Neutral, 2 = Disagree and 1 = Strongly Disagree. The instrument was subjected to Cronbach Alpha test of reliability which gave a high reliability alpha of above the 0.7 threshold prescribed by Nunnally, (1978).

The Structural Equation Modelling was deployed to test hypotheses, using a reflective, reflective and recursive model approach to predict the dependent variable. Convergence validity was determined based on the following thresholds: Standardized factor loadings >0.5 (Brown, 2014), Average variance extracted >0.5, and Composite reliability > 0.5 (Fornell&Larcker, 1981). Discriminant validity was assessed based on the criterion that "the square root of the average variance extracted must be greater than its correlations with all other constructs" (Fornell&Larcker, 1981).

Figure 1: Measurement Model of pro-activeness

Table 1: Measurement Model Analysis of pro-activeness

Model	Chi-Square(df), Significance	NFI	TLI	CFI	RMSEA	Variable	Standardized Factor Loading Estimates	Error VAR
Pro-activeness	(2df) =4.49, P<0.000	0.99	0.96	0.99	0.64	PA1	0.55	0.30
						PA2	0.71	0.50
						PA3	0.81	0.65
						PA4	0.72	0.51

Source: Amos 24.0 output on research data, 2019

Figure 2: Measurement Model of strategic partnership

Table 2: Measurement Model Analysis of strategic partnership

Model	Chi-Square(df), Significance	NFI	TLI	CFI	RMSEA	Variable	Standardized Factor Loading Estimates	Error VAR
Strategic partnership	(35df) =242, P<0.000	0.80	0.72	0.82	0.15	SP 1	0.65	0.43
						SP2	0.78	0.61
						SP3	0.71	0.51
						SP4	0.74	0.55
						SP5	0.66	0.43
						SP6	0.71	0.50
						SP7	0.64	0.40
						SP8	0.60	0.36
						SP9	0.45	0.24
						SP10	0.54	0.29

Source: Amos 24.0 output on research data, 2019

Table 3: Analysis of Moderating effect of Organizational Technology and the influence of entrepreneurial orientation on organizational survival of hotels in Port Harcourt.

Model (Recursive)	Chi-Square(df), Significance	NFI	TLI	CFI	RMSEA	Variable	Standardized Factor Loading Estimates	Error VAR
Organizational Technology	(1072df) =3264.71 P<0.000	0.59	0.65	0.68	0.18	Entrepreneurial Orientation	0.52	0.28
						Organisational Survival	0.52	0.31

Source: Amos 24.0 output on research data, 2018

Table 4: Correlations, Composite Reliability, Degree of freedom, Construct: Convergent and Discriminant Validity.

Variable	PRO	STRA	TECH	CR	Df	AVE
PRO	1.0	0.23	0.36	0.78	2	0.51
STRA	0.23	1.0	0.28	0.87	35	0.55
TECH	0.36	0.28	1.0	0.84	14	0.53

Note: PRO=Pro-activeness, STRA= Strategic Partnership, TECH= Organizational Technology, CR= Composite Reliability, AVE= Average Variance Extracted, Df= Degree of freedom.

Source: Amos 24.0 output on research data, 2019

Figure 3: Structural Model -Moderating effect of Organizational Technology

Convergence validity was determined based on the following thresholds:

(1) Standardized factor loadings >3.0, Degree of freedom >0 (Brown, 2014),

(2) Unstandardized factor loadings >0.8, Average variance extracted of all dimensions >0.5, and Composite reliability > 0.5 (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Discriminant validity was assessed based on the criterion that “the square root of the average variance extracted must be greater than its correlations with all other constructs” (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Test of Hypothesis

Table 5: Result of standardized and unstandardized regression estimate of the model.

S/N	Mediation Stage	Relationship	Std. Beta	Actual Beta	S.E	C.R	P	Remark
1	X → Y (Hypothesis 1)	Pro-activeness and Strategic partnership	0.36	0.78	0.11	3.21	0.000	Not supported
2	X → M M → Y (Hypothesis 2)	Technology Vs EO and OS.	0.62 0.75	0.97 0.85	5.3 0.83	2.47 3.32	0.000 0.000	Not supported

Source: Amos 24.0 output on research data, 2018

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between the pro-activeness and strategic partnership. Table 5 above illustrates the analysis for the association between pro-activeness and strategic partnership of SMEs in Nigeria, where $\beta=0.36$, $r=0.78$ and $p = 0.000$. The findings show a moderate and significant association between both variables (where $\beta>0.3$, $r>0.7$ and $p < 0.05$). Thus, based on the criteria for null hypothetical statement acceptance ($\beta<0.3$, $r<0.7$ and $p > 0.05$); or rejection ($\beta>0.3$, $r>0.7$ and $p < 0.05$), we reject the null hypothesis and restate that there is a positive significant relationship between pro-activeness and strategic partnership of SMEs in Nigeria. Therefore, Ho1 was not supported.

Ho2: Technology does not significantly moderate the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and organizational survival. Table 5 above illustrates the analysis for the moderating effect of Organizational Technology and the influence of entrepreneurial orientation on organizational survival of SMEs in Nigeria, where $\beta=0.61$, $r=0.96$ and $p = 0.000$. The findings show a very positive and significant association between both variables (where $\beta>0.3$, $r>0.7$ and $p < 0.05$). Thus, based on the criteria for null hypothetical statement acceptance ($\beta<0.3$, $r<0.7$ and $p > 0.05$); or rejection ($\beta>0.3$, $r>0.7$ and $p < 0.05$), we reject the null hypothesis and restate that technology significantly moderates the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and organizational survival of SMEs in Nigeria. Therefore, Ho2 was not supported.

Interpretation of Results and Discussion Findings:

The first hypothesis (Ho:1), states that there is no significant relationship between pro-activeness and strategic partnership. However, table 5 suggests that pro-activeness has a moderate and significant relationship with strategic partnership of hotels in South-South of Nigeria ($\beta=0.36$, $r=0.78$, $p<0.005$). Thus, Ho:1 was not supported. The means that the presence of pro-activeness, in hotels in Port Harcourt, will lead to strategic partnership with other hotels. Statistically, it shows that when pro-activeness goes up by 1 standard deviation, strategic partnership goes up by 0.36 standard deviation. In other words, when pro-activeness goes up by 1, strategic partnership goes up by 0.78. The regression weight for pro-activeness in the prediction of strategic partnership is significantly different from zero at the 0.005 level (two-tailed). Thus, it can be stated that the tendency for openness to change is a major criterion for the willingness and capacity to be open and ready to collaborate with other organizations and hotels. The evidence indicates that such behaviour which reflects pro-activeness possibly drives the hotels desire for learning and knowledge, which are some of the benefits obtained through such strategic partnerships and collaboration.

The second hypothesis (Ho:2), states that technology does not significantly moderate the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and organizational survival of hotels in the Port Harcourt. However, table 5 suggests that technology significantly moderates the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and organizational survival of hotels in the South-south of Nigeria ($\beta=$ for $X\rightarrow M=0.62$; $M\rightarrow Y=0.85$ and $X\rightarrow Y=1.74$, $p<0.005$). Therefore, Ho:10 was not supported. The result from the analysis reveals technology as having a strong and significant impact on the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and organizational survival of hotels in the South-south of Nigeria. Statistically, it shows that organizational technology is a good mediator of the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and organisational survival $\beta=$ for $X\rightarrow M=0.62$; $M\rightarrow Y=0.85$ and $X\rightarrow Y=1.74$, $p<0.005$). The evidence as illustrated in table 5 shows that organizational technology substantially effects and enhances the interaction between entrepreneurial orientations and organizational survival of hotels in Port Harcourt; thus, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected. The result for the multivariate analysis presents technology as a significant moderator of the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and organizational survival of hotels in the South-south of Nigeria. The evidence suggests that technology is essential to the extent to which organizations are able to innovate, are pro-active and confident in their capabilities. It drives the change development of the organization and allows it serve its clients or customers better using efficient and more sophisticated techniques. The result further demonstrates that technology is a major and substantial element of the functionality of the hotels as it provides the platform upon which superior services and products can be developed and also serves as the medium through which these services or products are communicated to the customers or clients. Thus it can be stated that: Technology enhances the impact of entrepreneurial orientation on the survival of hotels in the South-south of Nigeria.

Conclusions

On the basis of its observation and the empirical evidence, this study observed that:

1. Entrepreneurial orientation contributes significantly towards organization survival by the use of organizational technology.
2. Organizations thrive and survive on the basis of their ability to provide quality, distinct and convenient services to their customers; the case is no different for the Nigerian hospitality industry.

Recommendations

In view of the findings and the position of this study with regards the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and organizational survival of hotels in the South-South of Nigeria, this study recommends as follows:

- i. Hotel management and owners should focus on the challenges and observed inadequacies extant within their industry as a way of detecting which services can be redesigned creatively, to actualize distinction and uniqueness in service.
- ii. Technological systems should be designed to suit the changes and developments in the environment or industry of the business. That is say, organizations should adopt and utilize technological systems and infrastructures that enhance their functionality and should apply caution especially with the desire to appear “technologically inclined” and by that adopt overly grandiose systems that are inefficient and highly unsuitable for their environment.

Contribution to Knowledge

This study contributes to the body of knowledge by providing a holistic overview and detailed assessment of the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and organizational survival, using structural equations modeling (SEM) to provide strong evidence of goodness of fit. Thus, the study goes further by not only assessing correlations but also affirming the validity and structural fitness of the interaction between entrepreneurial orientation and organizational survival.

References

- Adewale, O.O., Abolaji, A. J., & Kolade, J. O. (2011). Succession planning and organizational survival: empirical study on Nigerian private tertiary institutions, *Serbian journal of management*, 6(2), 231-246
- Baridan D. M. (2001). *Research method in Administration Science*. Port Harcourt 2nd edition, Sherbrooke Associates.
- Brown, T. A. (2006). *Confirmatory factor analysis for applied research*. New York: Guilford Press.
- Chen, P. (2007). *Strategic management for small and medium enterprises*. Unpublished PhD Thesis, University of St. Clements, USA.
- Fornell, C., and Larcker, D. F. (1981). Evaluating Structural Equation Models with Unobservable Variables and Measurement Error. *Journal of Marketing Research* (18:1), pp. 39-50.
- Gaboul, A. F., & Fais, A. (2015). the effect of entrepreneurial orientation on organizational performance: a study of banks in Libya, *The journal of social science research*, 1(3) 25 - 31
- Gross, B. (2002). *Organizations and their managing*. New York: the free press, 454 growth, by New Zealand based quester companies.
- Groves, R.M., (1987). Research on survey data quality. *Public opinion Quarterly*, 51, 156-172.
- Gupta, A., Chen, X., & Gupta, V. K. (2016). Does management’s attention to different facets of entrepreneurial orientation create value for the firm? A longitudinal study of large retailers. Paper accepted for publication at *New England Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 19(2), 53-70.
- Gupta, V. K. (2015). Construction of entrepreneurial orientation: Dispute, demand, and dare. *New England Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 18(1), 87-89.
- Gupta, V. K., & Gupta, A. (2015). The concept of entrepreneurial orientation. *Foundations and Trends in Entrepreneurship*, 11(2), 55-137.
- Gupta, V. K., Dutta, D. K., & Chen, X. (2014). Entrepreneurial orientation capability and firm performance under conditions of organizational learning. *Journal of Managerial Issues*, 26(2), 157-173.
- Hult, G.T.M., Hurley, R.F. & Knight, G.A. (2004). Innovativeness: Its Antecedents and Impact on Business Performance. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 33, 429-438.
- Hult G. T. M, Snow, C.C., Kandemir, D. (2003). The role of entrepreneurship in building cultural competitiveness in different organizational types. *Journal of Management*, 29(3), 401 - 426.
- John, J. E., Micheal, U. A. & Cassiu, A. O. (2017). influence of entrepreneurial orientation as survival strategy for small and medium enterprises: the Nigerian experience, *International journal of economics, commerce and management*, 5(8), 502-518

- Jones, R., & Bartlet, D. (2008). The impact of catastrophes on shareholder value, the Oxford executive research briefings, Business at Oxford, Oxford, UK.
- Krejcie, R.V. & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining sample size for Research Activities. Educational and Psychological Measurement, 30, 607-610. Retrieved from https://home.kkv.ac.th/sompong/quest_speakers/krejcieandmorgan_article.pdf.
- Kuhn B., Sassmannshausen S.P., & Zollin, R. (2010). Entrepreneurial management as a strategic choice in firm behaviour: linking it with performance. Paper presented at the HTSF Conference in Twente, The Netherlands.
- Lekhanya, L. M. & Mason, R. B. (2014). The use of marketing strategies by small, medium and micro enterprises in rural KwaZulu-Natal. *SAJESBM*, 6,
- Likert, R. (1932). A technique for measurement of attitudes. *Archives of psychology*, 140,5-55
- Lumpkin, G.T. & Dess, G.G. (2014). Linking Two Dimensions of EO to Firm Performance: The Moderating Role of Environment and Industry Life Cycle. *Journal Business Venturing*, 16 (5), 429-451.
- Nunnally, J. C., & Bernstein, J. H. (1994). *Psychometric Theory* (3rd Ed.) New York: McGrawHill
- Rauch, A., Wiklund, J., Lumpkin, G.T. and Frese, M. (2009). EO and Business Performance: An Assessment of Past Research and Suggestions for the Future. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*. 33, 761-787.
- Stam, W. & Elfring, T. (2008). Entrepreneurial orientation and new venture performance: the moderating role of intra - and extra industrial social capital. *Academy of Management Journal*, 51(1), 97- 111
- Wiklund J., & Shepherd, D. (2003). Knowledge-based resources, entrepreneurial orientation, and the performance of small and medium sized businesses, *Strategic Management Journal*, 24(13), 1307-1314
- Yu-Ming, Wan-Qin, Sang-Bing, Wang, Zhao and Quan (2018). An Empirical Study on Entrepreneurial Orientation, Absorptive Capacity, and SMEs' Innovation Performance: A Sustainable Perspective. *Sustainability*, 10, 314; doi:10.3390/su10020314
- Zechir, F.A. (2015). Entrepreneurial Orientation and Firm Performance: The Role of Personality Traits in Malay Family Firms in Malaysia. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2 (1), 59-72

Cite this article:

Okoisama, T. C. & Ukoha, O. (2019). The Role of the Organizational Technology as a moderating Variable: Entrepreneurial Orientation and Organizational Survival of Hotels in Port Harcourt. *International Journal of Science and Business*, 3(2), 87-98. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2582477>

Retrieved from <http://ijsab.com/wp-content/uploads/329.pdf>

Published by

